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THE CEO POWER AND SUSTAINABILITY REPORTING OF LISTED FIRMS IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Purpose

This paper examines the influence of the CEO power among listed firms in Nigeria. Further, the study investigates the influence of CEO power on the sustainability reporting in a developing market, namely, the Nigerian market.

Design/methodology/approach

The study uses data from 2012 to 2021 with a total of 1120 observations and analyses the data using Logit regression analysis. Data are collected from the listed companies quoted on the Nigerian Exchange.

Findings

The authors found that CEO power, evidenced in CEO gender, CEO education, CEO tenure, CEO turnover, CEO ownership, CEO nationality reported by the Nigerian listed companies are significant. Regarding the specific individual influence of CEO power traits, they were found to significantly impact the sustainability reporting of listed firms in Nigeria.

Originality/value

This study enriches the literature by augmenting the understanding regarding CEO power's impact on sustainability reporting. Further, bringing evidence from an emerging market can have implications for regulators, shareholders, boards of directors, scholars, and researchers, students, who are interested in addressing other emerging markets with similar contextual and institutional environments.

Keywords: CEO power, CEO gender, CEO education, CEO tenure, CEO turnover, CEO ownership, CEO nationality, Nigeria, Sustainability reporting.

INTRODUCTION

The sustainability reporting of a firm is an important part of the firm's reporting regulatory requirements. Despite this position, there are limited or scarce empirical studies in the area of sustainability reporting/disclosure. Few scholars have published in the area of sustainability reporting (Gray, 2010; Hahn & Kuhnen, 2013; Simnett et al., 2009; Umar et al., 2021; Yahaya et al., 2022). Most of disclosure/reporting studies are on environmental disclosure (Al-Tuwaijri et al., 2004; Brammer & Pavellin, 2006; Clarkson et al., 2008; Cormier et al., 2004; Deegan & Gordon, 2012; Gray et al., 1995; Hackston & Milne, 1996; Lyon & Maxwell, 2011; Neu et al., 1998) and corporate social responsibility disclosure (Farook et al., 2011; Galant & Cadez, 2017; Gamerschlag et al., 2011; Khan, 2010; Lanis & Richardson, 2012; Platonova et al., 2018; Reverte, 2009; Roberts, 1992; Saleh et al., 2010; Teoh & Thong, 1984). There is need therefore to carry out more studies on sustainability reporting.

In the same vein, the CEO is the highest-ranking executive in a company. Generally, speaking, a chief executive officer's primary responsibilities include making major corporate decisions, managing the overall operations and resources of a company, acting as the main point of communication between the board of directors and corporate operations. In many cases, the chief executive officer serves as the public face of the company.

The CEO is elected by the board and its shareholders. The CEO reports to the chair and the board of directors, who are appointed by the shareholders. The CEO is in charge of day to day affairs of the company, including the preparation of annual reports and accounts of the company. Thus, it rests originally on the shoulders of the CEO to ensure that the annual reports and accounts of the company

include the sustainability report for the financial year. A CEO's role may vary from one company to another depending on the company's size, culture, and corporate structure. In large corporations, CEOs typically deal only with very high-level strategic decisions and those that direct the company's overall growth. For example, CEOs may work on strategy, organization, and culture. Specifically, they may look at how capital is allocated across the firm, or how to build teams to succeed. In smaller companies, CEOs often are more hands-on and involved with day-to-day functions. Thus, the CEO is in pole position to ensure that the company prepares and includes its sustainability report in the annual reports and accounts.

The Nigerian market is an emerging market by the World Bank classification. It is also called developing economy, which probably accounts for the low quality of sustainability reporting it is experiencing. It has one stock exchange, the Nigerian Exchange, with 156 listed firms, classified into 8 premium board (elite) firms, 134 main board founding firms, 4 alternative securities market firms and 6 small but growing firms. Of this 156 listed firms, 44 were excluded from our data set because of non-compliance with regulatory standards, established by the Nigerian Exchange Group, the trading floor provider in Nigeria. Therefore, a study of the variability in sustainability reporting is apt and appropriate in such an emerging market. The remaining sections are subdivided into literature review, methodology, results and discussion, and conclusion and recommendations.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Sustainability reporting (SR), also known as sustainability disclosure (SD) offers opportunities for firms to communicate their economic, environmental, social and governance performance to users of accounting information. Sustainability reporting is a form of non-financial reporting that enables companies to convey their progress toward goals on a variety of sustainability parameters, including environmental, social and governance metrics, as well as risks and impacts they may face, at the moment or in the future. In other words, sustainability reporting is a way to strengthen a firm's long-term strategy. In fact, sustainability reporting gives an overview of a company's economic, environmental and social impacts. Considering this statement, an organization is able to measure, understand and assess its performances.

The 'E', 'S', 'G' in ESG reporting stands for, "Environmental, Social, and

Governance” – otherwise known as the three key components that companies will use to determine the environmental efficacy and sustainability of their organization. Furthermore, there is a wide range of terminology used to qualify this same concept of sustainability reporting: non-financial reporting, extra-financial reporting, social reporting, CSR reporting or even socio-environmental reporting. However, in this paper, two terminologies are used: sustainability reporting or sustainability disclosure.

Simnett et al. (2009) seek to understand sustainability reporting by using a sample of 2,113 companies (from 31 countries) that produced sustainability reports between 2002 and 2004. They use sequential logit analysis to identify the factors associated with the decision to voluntarily provide sustainability reports. They hypothesize that a company's need to enhance credibility through the provision of sustainability reports is a function of company, industry, and country-related factors. Their results support the argument that companies seeking to enhance the credibility of their reports and build their corporate reputation are more likely to have their sustainability reports.

Greco et al. (2012) seek to respond to recent calls by the academic community for studies investigating sustainability reporting by the public sector, as well as for more engagement-based studies of this issue by examining the views of managers within local councils (LC). The objective of this project is to provide insights as to the possible reasons and explanations for the types of sustainability disclosures among a group of local councils operating in Italy and Australia. In particular, an international comparison is undertaken to ascertain the effect of culture on the adoption of sustainability reporting (SR). Evidence is collected from semi-structured interviews with managers and accountants from ten local councils consisting of five from Italy (Tuscany) and five from Australia (Victoria). The findings suggest that although there are available some general policy documents relating to sustainability reporting, councils are left to their own discretion as to what they consider fit under the definition of sustainability and therefore, determine to a large extent, what to report to stakeholders.

Hahn and Kuhnen (2013) provide a review of 178 articles dating from 1999 to 2011 from journals related to business, management, and accounting. Their aim is to identify what determinants of sustainability reporting are examined in the literature and to identify (in)consistencies, gaps, and opportunities for future research. They specifically illuminate factors influencing the adoption, the extent, and the quality of reporting. Based on their findings they provide an otherwise often missing link to theory (especially legitimacy, stakeholder, signaling, and institutional theory).

Hrebicek et al. (2015) provide current information dating from 2010 to 2014 from publications related to food and agriculture sector. The objective of the paper is to identify what determinants of SR are examined in the world initiatives to identify (in)consistencies, gaps, and opportunities for our future research of this field. The paper focuses on new G4 Guidelines of the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) and the Sustainability Assessment of Food and Agriculture (SAFA) systems of the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) of the United Nation. Also, possible future research of SR including SR information systems are discussed by illuminating gaps and underexposed themes in the area of regulation and governance as well as stakeholder perception.

Kuzey and Uyar (2016) investigate the factors that impact (1) Global Reporting Initiative-based sustainability reporting, (2) the adoption of assurance statements in sustainability reports, and (3) the application levels of sustainability reports. Moreover, (4) the paper examines whether sustainability reporting is value relevant or not based upon the sample provided by 297 Turkish publicly traded companies at the Borsa Istanbul. The findings reveal a growing awareness of Global Reporting Initiative-based sustainability reporting among the investigated corporations, and an improving trend in report quality; however, having sustainability reports assured by an independent verifier is not widespread among them. Using the basis of ten formulated hypotheses, the empirical evidence yielded significant results, which explain the driving factors behind sustainability reporting.

Sellami et al. (2019) provide a proof of the factors associated with sustainability assurance demand by French companies. This research used panel data methodology. The study results demonstrate that institutional ownership and the presence of corporate social responsibility (CSR) committee within the management board have an effect on the demand for sustainability assurance. The results also reveal that three types of stakeholders (employees, environment and customers) positively affect the demand of voluntary sustainability assurance.

Geerts et al. (2021) offer a multidimensional approach of the concept of sustainability reporting based on a global survey yielding 97 complete and valid answers of PMBs. A binomial logistic regression has been conducted to identify those organizational characteristics, whether or not under the control of the PMB, that have the largest explanatory power when it comes to the adoption of the practice of sustainability reporting. The results present new variables compared to the findings of previous studies, such as proximity to a city, the history of data gathering, and the presence of environmental/social certifications. Furthermore, this paper also investigates how these organizational characteristics are interlinked with external, contextual forces by making use of Institutional Theory. By

combining organizational characteristics with information on the institutional environment in which the PMB operates, a more complete image is obtained. The results of this analysis show that different institutional pressures are in play when it comes to having influence over the decision making of PMBs with regard to the adoption of sustainability reporting.

Furthermore, Hasan et al. (2021) investigate the determinants of corporate sustainability reporting decision. They use a logistic regression model to analyse data collected from a sample of 138 firms listed on the Pakistan Stock Exchange for the years 2009–2018. They find that firms with more gender-diverse boards, larger audit committees and higher institutional ownership are more likely to issue sustainability reports. They also find that concentrated ownership, managerial ownership, foreign ownership and audit committee independence negatively influence the firms' sustainability reporting decision.

Umar et al. (2021) assess the effects of sustainability reporting on the financial performance of 26 listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. The correlational research design was adopted for the study, and secondary data were collected from the annual reports and accounts of the firms for a period of 10 years (2009-2018). Multiple regression techniques used to analyse the data and diagnostic checks and post estimation tests were carried out on the data. The results show that social performance has a significant positive effect on financial performance. Similarly, results show that environmental performance has a significant positive effect on financial performance. However, results show that economic performance has a significant negative effect on financial performance.

Farisyi et al. (2022) aimed to find out how the development of sustainability reporting is seen from the theoretical and practical perspectives and how the solutions are solved. The study uses a systematic literature review approach via the PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) method, 24 selected articles were obtained that matched the criteria. The results show that research related to sustainability reporting currently focuses on nine aspects (variables): firm size, profitability, financial leverage, corporate governance structure, ownership structure, firm age, industrial sector, corporate posture, and board qualification and experience. However, from these studies, it was found that there were inconsistencies in the results. Some results showed that a determinant is significant in influencing the company's sustainability, whereas other studies indicated that the relationship between the two variables was not significant.

Yahaya et al. (2022) look at how board governance affects sustainability reporting for 2012 through 2021. The sample was 13 because it was limited to deposit money banks. The study adopted correlational research

design and the data were analyzed with the aid of multiple regression model based on Probit estimation. This study found board independence positive and significant, while board size, meeting, gender diversity, share ownership, and remuneration are insignificant.

Maama and Gani (2022) analyze the determinants of sustainability reporting of East African firms. Eight years of annual reports of 74 listed firms in Kenya, Tanzania, and Uganda were used. Random and fixed effect regression techniques were employed for the estimates. The study find that firms' specific characteristics such as size, Tobin's Q, industry affiliation, and ownership structure have a positive and significant influence on firms' management to adopt sustainability reporting practices. In addition, it was suggested that firms with a more considerable asset and Tobin's Q provide more sustainability reporting than those with smaller assets and Tobin's Q. The results further show that firms' age and return on assets do not influence sustainability reporting. The evidence further demonstrated that firms with foreign parent companies significantly disclosed more sustainability information than local firms.

Benvenuto et al. (2023) systematically review the literature to establish the distinctive elements of sustainability reporting and provide a complete theoretical framework that allows the classification of the drivers that are crucial for adopting sustainability reporting. Through the analysis, they describe the characteristic elements of sustainability reporting in a homogeneous and concise summary. The drivers that result, may prove useful not only in the context of non-financial reporting but also in encouraging adequate economic-business reflections that may inspire new research trajectories for scholars in this field.

Based on the six components of the CEO power, as reported earlier in section 1, the following the hypotheses are developed and tested:

H₁: CEO gender has no significant effect on sustainability reporting of listed firms in Nigeria.

H₂: CEO nationality has no significant effect on sustainability reporting of listed firms in Nigeria.

H₃: CEO tenure has no significant effect on sustainability reporting of listed firms in Nigeria.

H₄: CEO education has no significant effect on sustainability reporting of listed firms in Nigeria.

H₅: CEO turnover has no significant effect on sustainability reporting of listed firms in Nigeria.

H₆: CEO ownership no significant effect on sustainability reporting of listed firms in Nigeria.

In view of the foregoing review of both conceptual and empirical literature, the appropriate theory to underlie this study is the agency theory.

This is because agency theory helps to resolve the conflict of interests between the CEO on one hand, and the shareholders on the other. Agency theory is a concept used to explain the important relationships between principals, in this case, the shareholders and their relative agent, in this case, the CEO. In the most basic sense, the principal is someone who heavily relies on an agent to execute specific financial decisions and transactions that can result in fluctuating outcomes. Because the principal relies so heavily on the agent to make the right decision, there may be an assortment of conflicts or disagreements. Agency theory dives into such relationships.

METHODOLOGY

This section focuses on the research methodology regarding the measures of the variables by briefly explaining research design, research population, sample, sampling techniques, data collection methods and computation of dependent and independent variables used to examine the effect of CEO power on sustainability reporting. This study uses correlational research design and employs panel model using econometric analyses. The population is 156 listed firms on the Nigerian Exchange. 44 listed firms were excluded due to regulatory compliance flags, remaining 112 listed firms in the study's basket.

The econometric model of the study is:

$$SR_{i,t} = \alpha + CEOG_{i,t}\beta_1 + CEON_{i,t}\beta_2 + CEOE_{i,t}\beta_3 + CEOT_{i,t}\beta_4 + CEOTR_{i,t}\beta_5 + CEOO_{i,t}\beta_6 + \varepsilon_{i,t}$$

Whereas:

SR = Sustainability reporting, derived as an index from E, S and G information by .

E, measured as dummy where "1" is assigned to firm with annual reports with corporate environmental information disclosure and "0" for otherwise.

Social, measured as dummy where "1" is assigned to firm with annual reports with corporate social information disclosure and "0" for otherwise.

G, measured as dummy where "1" is assigned to firm with annual reports with corporate governance information disclosure and "0" for otherwise.

CEOG = CEO Gender, measured as dummy where "1" is assigned to companies that have Female CEOs and "0" for otherwise.

CEON = CEO Nationality, measured as dummy where "1" is assigned for companies that have foreign CEOs and "0" for otherwise.

CEO Education, measured as dummy where "1" is assigned to companies that have CEOs with PhD qualification and "0" for otherwise.

CEOT = CEO Tenure, measured as dummy where "1" is assigned to

companies that have CEOs that have stay for 3 years and "0" for CEOs with less than 3 years tenure.

CEOTR= CEO Turnover, measured as dummy where "1" is assigned to companies that have a change of CEOs in a particular year and "0" for otherwise.

CEO0 = CEO Ownership, measured as number of CEO shares divided by total numbers of shares (%).

α = Constant

β_{1-6} = Beta coefficients

ε = Error term (Residual)

i = Firm script (firms are 112)

t = Time script (10 years)

CEO data were extracted from the annual reports and accounts of the sampled listed firms from the database of the Nigerian Exchange website. Sustainability reporting data is an index developed from environmental, social and governance data, which were extracted using content analysis. Furthermore, diagnostic tests, such as normality of residuals, heteroskedasticity of residuals, multicollinearity among the CEO attributes, and panel effects were conducted in order to ensure that the model of the study is best linear unbiased estimator (BLUE). The data were analysed with the aid of STATA version 18.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section describes the results of diagnostic tests, including descriptive statistics, normality of residuals, heteroskedasticity of residuals, multicollinearity among the six variables of the CEO, panel effects test. Subsequently, multiple regression analysis is carried out using the Logit regression analysis. The results of descriptive analysis are reported in Table 1 with the observations, mean, standard deviation, min and max.

Table 1

Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
SR	1120	.456	.5	0	1
CEON	1120	.263	.441	0	1
CEOG	1120	.019	.136	0	1
CEOE	1120	.919	.274	0	1
CEOT	1120	.681	.467	0	1
CEOTR	1120	.194	.396	0	1
CEO0	1120	2.551	6.772	0	25.081

Source: STATA 18

From the results in Table 1, the number of observations is 1,120. The mean value of SR is .456 with a standard deviation of .5 and minimum and maximum values of 0 and 1. From these figures, a comparison between the mean and the standard deviation confirm that SR is highly volatile and unstable, which calls for interrogation. Also, a minimum mean of 0 means that some of the firms in our sample failed to disclosure their sustainability throughout the 10 year-period of this study. In addition, the maximum mean of 1 means that some of the firms in our sample disclosed their sustainability performance.

Furthermore, the mean value of CEON is .263 with a standard deviation of .441 and minimum and maximum values of 0 and 1. That is, the standard deviation is larger than the mean suggesting that some of the firms do not have a foreign CEO. Also, 0 and 1 minimum and maximum means imply that some of the firms have foreign CEO, while some other firms do not have. Additionally, the mean value of CEOG is .019 with a standard deviation of .136 and minimum and maximum values of 0 and 1. Again these figures show a high level of volatility and exposure in the variable. It suggests that most of the CEOs are men. In the same vein, the mean value of CEOE is .919 with a standard deviation of .274 and minimum and maximum values of 0 and 1. Also, the mean value of CEOT is .681 with a standard deviation of .467 and minimum and maximum values of 0 and 1. In addition, the mean value of CEOTR is .194 with a standard deviation of .396 and minimum and maximum values of 0 and 1. Finally, the mean value of CEOO is 2.551 percent with a standard deviation of 6.772 percent and minimum and maximum values of 0 and 25.081 percent. Furthermore, we carry out a number of diagnostic tests including normality of residuals, heteroskedasticity of residuals, model specification errors, multicollinearity and panel effects. The results of these tests are presented in Table 2 as follows.

Table 2

Results of post estimation tests

Serial	Test	Value
1	Normality of Residuals	.160
2	Homoscedasticity of Residuals	.161
3	Model Specification Error (ovtest)	.145
4	Multicollinearity (mean VIF)	2.12
5	Panel Effects	.207

STATA 16 Outputs

From the result of serial 1, in Table 2, it indicates that the residuals are normally distributed since the p-value of normality of residuals test is .160, which is slightly larger than .05 level of significance. The result in serial 2 indicates that there is no presence of homoscedasticity in the model and

therefore, there is no need to robust the regression model. The result in serial 3 indicates that there is no model specification error test, that is, the model is well specified. Similarly, the result in serial 4 shows that there is no multicollinearity among the independent. Finally, the panel effects test result shows that there is no panel effects in the model. Thus, the Logit regression model is the appropriate technique to use in this study since the dependent is measured by a dummy variable (0, 1).

Table 3 presents the results of Logit regression analysis, since the model shows that there are no panel effects.

Table 3

Results of Logit regression

SR	Coef.	St.Err.	z	p>z	[95% Conf	Sig
CEON	.14	.092	2.72	.013	.323	**
CEOG	.153	.305	3.60	.006	.448	**
CEOE	.081	.113	2.82	.047	.304	**
CEOT	.020	.013	3.82	.027	.311	**
CEOTR	.017	.134	2.22	.009	.281	***
CEOO	.008	.006	2.42	.022	.005	**
Constant	.53	.106	4.99	.000	.32	***
Pseudo R ²		0.760	Number of obs			
Chi ² -test		121.13	Prob > Chi ² = 0.022			

STATA 18 Outputs

From the results in Table 3, the effect of CEON on SR is significant. Therefore, hypothesis one is hereby rejected. In terms of result, it means that an increase in the number of foreign CEO brings about 14 percent increase in sustainability reporting. In the same vein, the effect of CEOG on SR is significant. Therefore hypothesis two is rejected. The result suggests that an increase in women CEO brings about 15.3 percent improvement in sustainability disclosure. In the vein, the effect of CEOE on SR is significant. Therefore, hypothesis three is rejected. This result brings about an improvement of 8 percent in sustainability reporting for CEO that has PhD. Similarly, CEOT shows significance with SR; bring a meagre improvement of 2 percent in sustainability reporting. Also, CEOTR shows significance with SR, bringing in 1.7 percent improvement in sustainability reporting. Finally, CEOO shows significance with SR; it also brings in about 1 percent improvement in sustainability reporting.

These results are in line with the works of scholars (Benvenuto et al., 2023; Farisyi et al., 2022; Greco et al., 2012; Greerts et al., 2021; Hahn & Kuyhnen, 2013; Hasan et al., 2021; Hrebicek et al., 2015; Kuzey & Uyar, 2016; Maama & Gani, 2022; Sellami et al., 2019; Simnet, 2009).

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study tries to fill in the gap by investigating how the CEO characteristics affect sustainability reporting via the 2012–2021 data of 112 Nigerian listed companies. Our empirical results show that CEO attributes, such as gender, nationality, tenure, turnover, education and ownership promote sustainability reporting within a threshold of 2012–2021. This paper makes a unique contribution to the literature by being the first to analyze the effects of CEO power on sustainability reporting using a Nigerian representative sample. However, the research can be further extended by focusing on other sources of CEO power, such CEO duality, age, ethnicity or race. Furthermore, research could be conducted to determine the effects of women CEO on sustainability disclosure among listed firms in Nigeria. It could also focus on the differences in impact between publicly listed firms and private companies. Research could also determine the effects of specific policies or initiatives to increase CEO diversity on sustainability disclosure. Additionally, the study could be conducted to explore the impact of CEO power on different types of sustainability (ESG) disclosure.

This research could benefit investors and other stakeholders in the corporate world, as it would provide insight into the potential roles associated with investing in the CEO. The implications suggest that actions be taken by both government regulators, shareholders, boards of directors, scholars/researchers, students and enterprises to promote interaction between the CEO and sustainability reporting. Sustainability reporting models should be updated for Nigerian listed firms and promote it through the reinforcement of the collaborations of regulators, shareholders, boards of directors, enterprises, universities and institutes.

Author Contributions:

All the authors participated equally in all phases of the research reported in the article, including conceptualization, methodology, software use, validation, formal analysis, investigation, resources, data cure, writing—original draft preparation, writing—review and editing, visualization, supervision, and project administration. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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